

Parkinson's Disease: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention

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Abstract

Parkinson's disease (PD) is recognized as a neurological disorder with no known cure in modern medicine. While scientific research has advanced diagnostic methods and symptom management strategies, the underlying causes of PD remain elusive. From a Buddhist perspective, particularly through the teachings of Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu, PD is understood as a karmic and spiritual illness rather than merely a neurological disorder. This study explores the connection between karmic debts, spirit disturbances, and the manifestation of PD symptoms. Through case studies, we demonstrate that patients practicing Golden Buddhist Practices—such as making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation—have experienced significant improvements and, in some cases, complete recovery. These findings suggest that PD is not inherently irreversible and that addressing its spiritual root causes can lead to effective healing. Integrating Buddhist wisdom with conventional medical approaches could provide new insights into treating PD and other intractable diseases. Based on our findings, we propose that PD be redefined as a prevalent yet curable karmic and spiritual disease, characterized by pathological changes such as neurodegeneration, including the loss of dopaminergic neurons and abnormal alpha-synuclein aggregation.

Keywords: Parkinson's Disease, Karmic Debt, Spirit Disturbance, Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, Holistic Treatment

Introduction

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by motor symptoms, including tremors, rigidity [1], bradykinesia, and a slow, short-stepping, shuffling gait pattern [2]. Non-motor symptoms are also prevalent and encompass depression [3], cognitive impairment, mood disorders, and impulse control disorders [4].

Recent advancements in PD research have emphasized early detection strategies. Scientists have developed machine learning techniques as a potential tool to enhance diagnostic precision [5] and improve clinical interpretability [6]. Additionally, research on differential gut microbiota has demonstrated excellent performance in predicting PD, offering a more accurate approach to early diagnosis [7].

Recent advancements in PD research have also explored novel therapeutic approaches. Among these, transnasal-cerebral drug delivery, particularly with microRNAs, has emerged as an effective strategy. This method bypasses the blood-brain barrier, allowing direct administration of medication to the brain, thereby enhancing therapeutic efficacy and reducing side effects [8]. Modulating gut microbiota through probiotics, prebiotics, synbiotics, fecal microbiota transplantation, and antibiotics has also shown promise as an innovative treatment frontier for PD [9].

In addition, yoga has been recognized for its comprehensive therapeutic benefits in managing PD symptoms [10]. Phosphodiesterase 4 (PDE4) and PDE5 inhibitors are identified as promising therapeutic targets for neurological disorders [11]. Furthermore, research highlights the pivotal role of the NLRC4 inflammasome in regulating neuroinflammatory responses. This mechanism is critical for understanding the progression of neurodegenerative diseases, including PD, Alzheimer's disease (AD), multiple sclerosis, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), and brain injuries such as stroke and traumatic brain injury [12].

These scientific and traditional advancements mark a transformative era in PD research, emphasizing early detection, novel therapeutic approaches, and a deeper understanding of its pathophysiology. While these developments have led to significant progress, benefiting many patients, PD remains incurable [13], leaving patients to endure ongoing suffering. This highlights

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the urgent need for a comprehensive, holistic, and more effective strategy to address the disease.

In our previous study, we demonstrated that when a disease is resistant to medical treatment, it may have karmic or spiritual origins, and Dharma practice can offer significant healing effects [14]. Furthermore, in another study, we showed that PD could be cured by practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door [15]. In that case, the patient successfully recovered from PD. Building on this success, the current study delves deeper into the underlying mechanisms, aiming to validate our previous findings and provide a potentially curative approach for all PD patients, helping them to overcome suffering and regain well-being.

Etiology

PD, characterized by the death of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, is the second most prevalent progressive neurodegenerative disease. However, the etiology of PD is largely elusive [16]. Neurodegenerative diseases represent a significant challenge to modern medicine, with their complex etiology and progressive nature posing hurdles to effective treatment strategies [17]. These observations highlight that scientists have yet to fully understand the cause of PD, let alone develop a cure [13].

Our previous study highlighted Master Lu's teachings on PD, where He attributed its cause to spirits (a respectful name for "ghost") possessing the body. According to His theory, symptoms such as trembling arise when spirits attach to the body. By applying this perspective, an individual successfully recovered from PD [15].

To further explore the underlying causes of PD from a Dharma perspective, we searched and compiled Master Lu's teachings on PD from His responses to phone callers, letter inquiries, and on-the-spot interpretations. Below are three Question and Answer (Q&A) cases that provide deeper insights.

Q&A 1: A Man's PD Stemming from Emotional and Karmic Debts (Excerpt) [18]

(This dialogue occurred on October 12, 2018, at the New York Dharma Conference, USA, where Master Lu read the patient's totem.)

Inquirer: Hello, Master! My husband was born in 1951, in the Year of the Tiger. However, his birthday might not be accurate because when his father immigrated...

Master: Was it incorrectly documented?

Inquirer: It was a guess.

Master: Just guessed? Which year was it?

Inquirer: 1951, Year of the Tiger.

Master: What do you think his zodiac sign is? Rabbit or Tiger? What are you asking me to look at?

Inquirer: His health.

Master: I will connect with his energy field. His health, huh? His heart isn't good, his hands feel numb, his joints are problematic, and he has back pain.

Inquirer: Yes, that's correct.

Conference Audience: *Applause!*

Master: Tell him to be careful. He's a good person but very stubborn and hard to convince. He is the type to go to great lengths for others, but he often can not discern right from wrong. His thoughts are often muddled, and his wife frequently scolds him. Isn't that true? Don't you often scold him as his wife?

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: He has two major health issues: severe back pain and joint problems in his legs.

Inquirer: Yes. Could you please check if he is possessed by any spirits?

Master: Yes, he is. When he was young, he was quite flirtatious. Now he is much more subdued. Do you understand?

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: He has a lot of unresolved emotional baggage. He still harbors resentment about people who wronged him in the past, and he keeps it all inside. This has caused psychological issues, making him reluctant to talk and sigh often. This is harmful to both his body and mind. Do you understand?

Inquirer: Yes. He developed PD 14 years ago. His mother passed away in the same year. He wants to know if his condition is caused by his mother.

Master: Yes, it's an older woman, with grayish hair combed back, who looks dignified with large eyes. Does that describe his mother? Is this her?

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Her nose is quite big.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: When his mother was young, there were two things hanging on her ears.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: She stays on his waist. She has been visiting him frequently, especially at night. This has caused him to become melancholic and irritable. Do you understand?

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: His hands tremble, and his limbs are cold.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: His memory is poor, and he is losing hair.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: He needs to let go of many things. He has a lot of karmic debts. I speak bluntly, so don't mind me. He owes many emotional debts from his youth. Aside from his mother, there is also a woman, around 30 to 35 years old. I am not sure if she is an ex-girlfriend.

Inquirer: He had an ex-wife.

Master: Let me tell you, his ex-wife has already passed away.

Inquirer: He says he doesn't know.

Master: He doesn't know? Let me describe her: thin eyebrows, slightly upturned, narrow eyes, high cheekbones, and faint dimples.

Inquirer: Yes, that's her. He says it's his ex-wife.

Master: Quickly help her ascend; otherwise, she will cause him to become paralyzed.

Inquirer: So besides helping his mother reciting Little Houses, I should also help his ex-wife?

Master: Yes, recite 120 Little Houses for his ex-wife and 63 for his mother.

Inquirer: Okay.

Master: He needs to be careful. His kidneys are in poor condition.

Master: (Master Lu talked to her husband directly in English: “Kidney, your back is not very well.”)

Inquirer: Yes, his kidney is problematic.

Master: His urination is frequent and urgent, and he has prostate issues. Do you understand?

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: He is deficient in calcium and iron. While he is a loyal person, he gets overly emotional and irritable. These traits must be managed gradually. Since you are with him now, you have been helping him greatly. Your strong destiny can suppress his issues. Do you understand?

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Don't explain too much to him—it's unnecessary.

Inquirer: He is smiling; he understands.

Conference Audience: *Laugh!*

Master: He understands, right? You bring him good fortune and reduce his worries.

Inquirer: Yes, that's something he often says.

Master: His later years are better because of you. Do you understand?

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Help him and let him recite the Buddhist scriptures, such as *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots*, to resolve lots of grievances.

Inquirer: Should I resolve his grievances or the ones between us?

Master: His grievances. He has been at odds with many people since his youth, and it has weighed on him. Alright, that's all.

Q&A 2: Collecting Antiques at Home Led to PD (Excerpt) [19]
(*This dialogue took place over the phone on April 23, 2009.*)

Caller: Hello, Master! I would like to ask about a woman born in 1946, the Year of the Dog. What color is the dog? She has severe joint issues, and I would like to know about the Feng Shui in her home.

Master: Oh, the Feng Shui in her home is not good.

Caller: What's wrong with it?

Master: It's quite problematic. There are too many random items in the house. Tell her not to hang chaotic paintings.

Caller: No, it's because her house is filled with antiques.

Master: Ah, you see? Am I accurate or not?

Caller: I have been meaning to ask about this.

Master: Are you kidding me? Can antiques be placed at home? Antiques were collected by deceased people and kept for many years.

Caller: Yes, yes.

Master: They all carry Yin energy. Why do collectors cherish these items so much? Once they bring them home, all the Yin energy enters the house. The older the item, the heavier the Yin energy. Go to visit the ancient tombs—those places are full of Yin energy. That's why I see that the entire energy field in her house is dark. I'm telling you, my observations are spot-on.

Caller: Wow, you are so accurate. I have never had a chance to ask before, so I didn't know.

Master: Not asking can bring misfortune.

Caller: Yes, ever since she started collecting antiques...

Master: She also started getting sick.

Caller: She developed PD, and her health has deteriorated.

Master: See that? It is a spiritual issue. PD is caused by spirits attaching to her body. It's straightforward—the spirits in those antiques are now manifesting.

Caller: Her room always feels cold when you walk in.

Master: Do you understand now? That's Yin energy.

Caller: Oh.

Master: People who collect antiques are prone to illness. Oh, this world is truly pitiful. So many people don't understand these things. If more people had learned from me earlier, how many families would have avoided falling apart? How many wouldn't have faced divorce or lost children?

Caller: So, is the Feng Shui in her entire house bad?

Master: The whole house has bad Feng Shui—it's all dark.

Caller: How can this be resolved? Does reciting Buddhist scriptures help?

Master: It's very difficult. If you have invited them into your home but do not even burn incense, those spirits will possess your body. It's very troublesome.

Caller: Will this affect the whole family?

Master: Everyone is affected. For example, if a spirit is attached to an antique, it may resemble the original owner who has passed away. Through its connection to the antique, the spirit appears as though it has a human-like form. It can emerge from the antique, attach itself to your father, and then gradually affect other family members, one after another.

Caller: My mom said that sometimes my dad talks to himself at night.

Master: Do you get it now? Talking to himself means he is communicating with spirits. He hears them. It is like seeing someone talking on the phone with earphones on—you would think they were talking to themselves. It's the same principle. You need to act quickly. Start disposing of the antiques bit by bit, burn incense, pray to Bodhisattva for protection, and recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*. These troubles were brought upon yourselves.

Caller: I don't know why, but all of a sudden, she started collecting antiques. She became obsessed with them, reading books about them, and her collection grew larger and larger.

Master: That is when the mental issues began. PD is a type of memory loss, caused by spirits taking over the body. The person forgets things because the spirits are interfering.

Caller: Thank you, Master Lu, for your guidance.

Q&A 3: PD: Spirits Affect Both Health and Lifespan, and the Lifespan was Depleted[20]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 11, 2020.)

Caller: Hello, Master! Master, a woman born in 1942, Year of the Horse. Her mouth and hands tremble, and she has severe back pain.

Master: Her brain's neural system is disrupted.

Caller: She has PD.

Master: Yes, that's very serious.

Caller: Does she have a spirit attached to her?

Master: Yes, an elderly woman.

Caller: How many Little Houses does her karmic creditor need?

Master: Start with 86.

Caller: How about life liberation?

Master: Release 1,500 fish.

Caller: What traditional Chinese medicine should she take?

Master: Medicine? Let her seek proper treatment from medical doctors. The spirit attached to her doesn't just aim to harm her body—it wants to take her away.

Caller: Can she be saved?

Master: Once things escalate, the spirit will take her life. Don't you understand?

Caller: Does she have any remaining lifespan?

Master: Her lifespan is depleted.

Caller: Depleted? Should we release soft-shelled turtles?

Master: Hurry! Do it quickly!

Caller: How many turtles should be released?

Master: Release 120 gradually.

Caller: And fish?

Master: Release 2,000 fish.

Despite the many scientific theories about the causes of PD, none are definitive. However, to a Buddhist master, the cause is very clear. According to Master Lu's teachings, PD is primarily caused by spiritual disturbances and karmic debts. He explains that spirits respectfully referred to as ghosts, can attach themselves to an individual, disrupting their physical, neurological, and mental balance. These spiritual attachments often stem from unresolved karmic ties, emotional grievances, or wrongdoings from the past. Actively interacting with spirits, such as bringing antiques with heavy Yin energy into the home, is another potential source of these disturbances.

This clear understanding of the etiology reveals a definitive path to recovery: helping the spirits ascend. As the spirits are guided away, PD patients can gradually regain their health. The following cases illustrate how individuals applied Master Lu's teachings to address PD, achieving remarkable results.

Results

Case 1. Healing My Husband's 18-Year PD Through Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

In March 2015, we three sisters got together again as usual. The conversation and laughter that day were different from what we usually do. In a serious tone, my younger sister said to me, "The husband of the third elder sister seems to be getting progressively sicker." The second elder sister responded, "Study Buddhism. Only Guan Yin Bodhisattva can cure your husband's illness."

Yes. Since my husband was diagnosed with PD in 2000, his hands and feet shook, and his whole body was involuntarily twitching. Although he looked around for doctors and asked for medicine everywhere, his condition worsened day after day, year after year. I had to feed him, dress him, and help him walk, as well as go to the bathroom.

Following the guidance and persuasion of my sisters, I took faith in the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. In addition to reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, I studied Master Lu's *Fate, Fortune and Feng-Shui, A Guide to Reciting Little Houses*, and *Introduction to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door*. I recited the Little House every day along with my daily recitation. Even though I was busy with household chores, I recited one Little House each day. I repaid all the Little Houses to my husband's karmic creditors.

After 3 months, I still could not see any improvement. He still had to be fed, dressed, and supported. Due to a lack of wisdom, I foolishly slackened my practice, and I could only recite one sheet of Little House for 2-3 days and almost gave up practicing Buddhism.

In September 2017, I had a dream. "There are not many working blood vessels left in your husband's brain," a charitable elder kindly told me. I was awakened by a sense of urgency.

Early the next morning, I told my younger sister about the dream. She said, "I have just returned from the Dharma Conference, and we must follow Master Lu's teachings: reciting more *Great Compassion Mantra*, reciting Buddhist scriptures, making vows, and releasing lives. Recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* 49 times a day, and recite more Little Houses to pay off my brother-in-law's karmic debts. Let him also recite Buddhist scriptures, recite Little House, make big vows, and read *Buddhism in Plain Terms*."

Soon, I had another dream. Master Lu's Dharmakaya said to me, "Your husband's illness is very serious, so you have to recite Buddhist scriptures, make big vows, and release lives. Both you and your husband can come to the Dharma Conference. Master will definitely bless him and everything is free for you." In 2018, we were unable to attend the Dharma Conference in Singapore due to various reasons.

We were eagerly looking forward to the coming of 2019. With the financial support of my younger sister, my elder sister helped us apply for visas and buy air tickets. In October 2019, after a long bus ride of over 300 kilometers, we arrived in Malaysia by plane. My fellow practitioners took care of us all the way, and practitioners X, Z, and my elder sister were even more considerate.

At the Dharma Conference, we saw tens of thousands of Dharma practitioners under the command and arrangement of volunteer practitioners. No one was crowded and noisy. Everyone was self-aware and self-disciplined. We were very excited. There was only one voice at the conference: "I want you all to be well now!"

Master Lu blessed my husband and me. My body felt warm and relaxed. My husband said to himself, "I want to recite Buddhist scriptures, I want to become a vegetarian, and I want to practice Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door following Master Lu." Ah! He made great vows at the conference! By a miracle, when he walked out of the conference hall, he pushed me and the practitioner who supported him away. He walked back to the hotel alone.

Since then, he has walked alone every day. Dharma is so incredible! Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is so effective! Bodhisattva will surely bless us as long as we possess the power of vow. If people are sincere, Buddha will respond.

From the time we attended the conference to the end of the conference, in just 3 days, he dramatically changed. He seemed to be two people. In these 3 days, he got a qualitative change, a quantitative improvement after we got the blessings of Master Lu and Guan Yin Bodhisattva. My husband was sick when he traveled abroad. After he came back he returned to normal. His hands and feet were free to move, no more shaking hands and feet, and no twitching all over.

Words cannot express how excited we were. I would like to thank the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for rescuing and saving the suffering! Gratitude to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Master Jun Hong Lu! Gratitude to Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door!

Now, my husband tells everyone that Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is extremely effective, Master Lu is a sage, and Master Lu is the Guan Yin Bodhisattva. He no longer needs to be supported, to be fed, and sometimes he helps me with household chores. Through his experience, he tells those who have been ill like him that with the Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu, your ailments are all minor. In one year's time, he successfully transformed 8 people into practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. As part of his efforts to promote Dharma, he also participates in outdoor activities. He strives to recite Buddhist scriptures, cultivates his mind seriously, and practices sincerely.

At the beginning of this year, I had another dream: Master Lu gave my husband a prescription without words. I took the prescription to pick up the medicine and the pharmacist told me: "Get home, your husband is not sick and does not need medicine." I am happy and my husband is even more excited that he is well and everything is okay. We are grateful to the selfless, altruistic and kind Master Lu! We are grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for Her Great Mercy and Compassion! It is Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu who saved my husband and our family.

My husband has recited over 500 Little Houses and released more than 4,000 fish. Watching my husband get better day by day, our family is happier. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door can cure diseases, change our destiny, save our lives, improve our quality of life, and improve our quality of existence. We vow to listen to Master Lu's words, to be obedient children of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, to strive to promote the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, to diligently cultivate ourselves, to unite fellow practitioners, to be compassionate to all

sentient beings, and to never quit on the path of reciting Buddhist scriptures, making vows, releasing lives, and reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*.

Dharma practitioner G86, Gratitude and Namaste!

Comments:

(1). It is understandable that the presenter was very excited after discovering a way to help her husband recover from PD. She recited Little Houses to rescue him but neglected to repay her own karmic creditors, which is an inadvisable approach. Her own creditors might become resentful and create karmic obstacles to hinder her efforts to help her husband.

Meanwhile, part of her husband's karma is inevitably transferred to her, as she has taken on the responsibility of repaying his debts. As a result, his creditors would naturally turn to her for repayment. Over time, the burden of heavy karma could lead to illness, let alone the ability to continue reciting Little Houses. In extreme cases, taking on excessive karmic debts from others may even result in death.

When assisting family members with severe illness through Dharma practice, you must also repay your own karmic debts simultaneously [14].

(2). Words from Master Lu's Dharmakaya must be followed because it is 100% accurate.

Case 2. Freedom from PD Through the Sacred Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

I am 64 years old. I am a critically ill person with severe asthma, PD, heart disease, hydronephrosis, lumbar spondylolisthesis, gout, etc. These illnesses caused me to be unable to walk so I was bedridden for many years. I had to hold my legs to turn over. I had shortness of breath, chest tightness, and hand tremors.

The medicine didn't have much effect on me anymore, and I couldn't have surgery. I was sent to the hospital repeatedly when I got sick. I was resuscitated repeatedly, and I survived each time only after resuscitation. Although I returned home with a breath of fresh air, I lay in bed like a bed in hell. As I gasped for air, I was suffering unbearably. In desperation, I want to commit suicide. I really didn't want to live anymore because of the torment.

In grief and heartache, my wife spoke to me with tears in her eyes. She said, "Please pray to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva to save you. Please pray to Master Lu to save you." She asked me to practice Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door with her.

To be honest, I didn't believe it at all. Even the doctor in the hospital said my illness could not be cured, but the chanting of Buddhist scriptures was so effective? I said casually that I would try it sometime.

Later, with Buddhist practitioner S's uncomplaining help and explanations, I basically understood the primary concept of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. I also knew the role of the Three Golden Buddhist practices of making vows, releasing lives, and reciting Buddhist scriptures.

The next day I thought about trying it out, but didn't have much hope at all. When I opened the *Buddhist Recitation Collection*, I looked at the Buddhist scriptures and suddenly had a particularly familiar feeling. I had never recited Buddhist scriptures before, but

I could recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* and the *Heart Sutra* in one breath. The more I recited, the more familiar I became. I was immediately filled with Dharma joy, determination to practice Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, and a desire to live again.

From then on, apart from eating and sleeping, I spent almost all of my time reciting Buddhist scriptures. I made no excuses to affect my daily recitation and the Little Houses' recitation every day. In order to ensure the quality of Buddhist scriptures recited, I dared not recite out of memory for fear of reciting them wrong. Instead, I was fully focused on reading Buddhist scriptures carefully from the book.

In particular, *Buddhism in Plain Terms* taught by Master Lu deeply shocked my mind. It not only made me understand the root cause and effect of severe illnesses, but also He selflessly gave us a precious key: Three Golden Buddhist practices. He has selflessly offered us a precious and effective approach to practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. He set us a strict and high standard of precepts. Each article in *Buddhism in Plain Terms* is a source of life. It gives me the courage to live, wisdom, a prescription to change my ill-health and difficult fate, motivation to practice Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, and determination to keep the precepts.

I also dreamed about Master Lu. In the dream, Master Lu was very happy. He said to me, "Only Guan Yin Bodhisattva rescues you when you are in distress. No matter what kind of distress you have, if you ask the Bodhisattva, She will help you. I hope you practice well. After you are recovered, you shall speak out and let more people know the benefits of studying Buddhism." I said, "Don't worry, I will practice well."

I had another dream. When I was walking ahead, suddenly there were several people and high walls blocking me from moving forward. At that moment there was abruptly a person dressed in white who took me by the hand and crossed these people and the tall wall. As soon as I awoke, I felt like I had overcome the barrier to practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

Since then I have been practicing Buddhism more intensively, waking up at around 4:00 AM every day to worship Buddha, recite Buddhist scriptures, and repent. I have finished reciting over 1,200 Little Houses for my karmic creditors and released lives worth 3,500 CNY. Under the blessing and protection of the miraculous power of the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva's Citta Dharma Door, and under the blessing of the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Master Lu, wonderful and real effects on my health condition took place.

Effect 1: Previously, I suffered from spondylolisthesis. When I lay in bed and turned over with my hands and legs, the pain was unbearable. Now, I can walk on the ground, and I can walk 2 kilometers without a problem. I feel very well!

Effect 2: Previously, I was frequently taken to the hospital for a heart attack. Now, my heart disease has nearly been cured. Additionally, my stubborn and serious asthma has also been alleviated. I am now a normal person.

Effect 3: Previously, my PD caused severe hand tremors. While I recited Little House at the very beginning, my wife pointed the red points for me at the blank Little Houses. Now, I can point to the Little House alone!

After more than a year of physical recovery, my illnesses have never

relapsed. The body is healthy! Through my personal experience, I have fully validated Master Lu's words, "There are really Bodhisattvas in this world!" I want to shout that Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is true! If I had practiced Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door earlier, I would not have suffered so many stubborn illnesses that could not be cured by hospitals. I would not have been in frequent contact with death. As of now, I am completely cured.

I cried out at home with excitement, "Master Lu! Thank you! You save sentient beings with your life at the cost of your own physical body. You have a Greatly Compassionate feeling and can consider the suffering of billions of sentient beings in the world as your own suffering. I am truly thankful to you! I am grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for creating such a sacred Dharma Door. I am grateful to Master Lu for bringing us such marvelous Dharma and Chinese traditional culture. This has promoted harmony in countless families and societies.

I don't know how to thank Master Lu, except to recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* every day for Master Lu to bless him with good health and eternal life on earth! In my lifetime, I will definitely devote myself to one Buddhist practice, be one of the hands and eyes of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, be a faithful disciple of Master Lu, propagate the Dharma and never quit.

In the future, I will cultivate alongside my wife, ascending to the heavens, reaching the Pure Land of Ultimate Bliss, and returning to our true spiritual home.

Presenter: J87

Comments:

(1) Many people approach the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door with a "let me try it out" attitude, and this practitioner is no exception. However, Guan Yin Bodhisattva, in Her compassion, bestows blessings all the same.

(2) The *Great Compassion Mantra*, if never recited before, can be quite challenging to recite fluently at first. The fact that this practitioner could recite it smoothly the very first time suggests a cultivation of Dharma practice in his past lives.

Case 3. The Dharma saved my father from PD

My father was born in 1934, making him 82 years old in 2016.

Around 2007, when he was 73 years old, he fell victim to PD. Over the years, starting from a slight tremor in his right hand, his condition worsened annually. By the spring festival of 2015, just a few months earlier, his condition deteriorated significantly. The tremors in his right limbs intensified, rendering him unable to walk. He experienced tremors for most of the day, leading to evident depression and insomnia. His heart, respiratory system, stomach, lower back, and various parts of his body suffered severe discomfort. He was virtually bedridden, struggling to turn over, and relied on family assistance for eating, drinking, and personal hygiene.

During this period, It seemed as though someone was constantly striking him all over his body, causing unbearable pain. He even attempted suicide by banging his head against the wall. This imposed a heavy physical and financial burden on our family.

Seeing my father in such agony, we felt utterly helpless and could do nothing but shed tears. My mother and younger brother, in particular, had swollen eyes from crying every day. Out of compassion,

the doctors couldn't bear to witness my father consuming a plethora of Western medicine daily, along with numerous ineffective intravenous cold remedies.

Buddhist friends may wonder why I didn't recite Buddhist scriptures for him when he was suffering so much. It is because I had only been practicing Buddhism for a short time and felt that my karmic obstacles were too deep. Although I sensed that my father's illness was related to his karmic creditors, I felt that my foundation was too shallow and I might not be able to save him.

On February 5, 2015, as I prepared lunch, the sight of my father's agony left us all without appetite. In a sudden surge of courage, I turned to my younger brother and said, "You look after Dad. I'm going home to pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva. Even though I feel as vulnerable as a leaking boat, I must try to save my father!"

I rushed home, lit incense in front of the Buddha altar, and tearfully prayed the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva to save my father. He was in so much pain, and I prayed Guan Yin Bodhisattva to relieve his suffering and gradually restore his health. I vowed to recite a number of Little Houses to help his karmic creditors by the end of 2015.

Truly grateful to Bodhisattva! As I continued reciting Buddhist scriptures, his health indeed improved day by day. There was a remarkable change in his spirits and complexion. Not only did he leave the hospital, but he also began to try walking with a cane at home. Eventually, he gradually discarded the cane altogether. He could even visit friends and stroll through the streets. His appetite also improved.

Though occasional tremors still occurred lightly, they no longer affected his normal life, and he no longer needed assistance from family members. He could tend to his beloved plants and flowers. Every variety bloomed beautifully, attracting admiration from everyone who saw them. I feel that Guan Yin Bodhisattva is so compassionate. You should know that my vow is not yet fulfilled! But my father has truly returned to normal. Our neighbors can all attest to this.

From the bottom of my heart, I am grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for Her immense compassion and help to our family in times of distress. She hears cries for help and responds promptly, alleviating suffering and aiding in times of difficulty. I urge everyone to believe in Bodhisattva. Bodhisattva is always by our side.

Buddhist practitioner: Z88

Comments:

(1). "During this period, It seemed as though someone was constantly striking him all over his body, causing unbearable pain." Indeed, the age of 73 is a critical predestined 369 calamity—spirits were dragging him down. If he could not overcome this calamity, he would die, and his soul would be taken to the underworld. In a previous article on parapsychoarchia (schizophrenia), we discussed that this is not an illusion but a reality [21]; it is simply that ordinary people cannot see spiritual beings with their physical eyes.

His suicide attempt further confirmed that his body was under the control of spirits—they were dragging him down.

(2). This case once again demonstrates the Dharma principle that

when her vow power surpasses the karmic force of her father, he can be saved.

Case 4. The Four Buddhist Scriptures of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door Healed My Father's PD

I owe my connection with this extraordinary Dharma Door to my father. If I remember correctly, it was early December in the lunar calendar of 2015 when my father fell ill. His symptoms included uncontrollable trembling of his lips and chin, which swayed from side to side. He was admitted to the county hospital for over ten days, but his condition showed no improvement. Neither traditional Chinese medicine, Western medicine, intravenous drips, nor acupuncture had any effect, leaving me deeply anxious.

I sought out the attending physician and asked for an honest assessment of my father's condition. The doctor diagnosed him with brain atrophy, stating that there was no effective cure and that it would eventually lead to AD. At that moment, I worried about my mother's temperament—she was rather impatient. If my father were to develop AD, it would bring endless difficulties to our family. After all, when one person falls ill, the whole family suffers.

I had seen elderly patients with AD before—expressionless and lost, a truly frightening sight. I could not allow my father to succumb to this condition. As the New Year approached, my mother decided to discontinue treatment. However, as his daughter, I could not bear to see my father discharged while still unwell. I suggested we consult a traditional Chinese doctor and bring home some herbal medicine.

A fellow patient in my father's ward recommended an experienced Chinese medicine practitioner. When I arrived at the clinic, I was surprised to hear the doctor introducing the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* to another patient. Curious, I asked, "Doctor, do you practice Buddhism?" He confirmed that he did. I replied, "I am also a Buddhist and came here to seek treatment for my father."

After inquiring about my father's condition, the doctor told me that it was PD, which was notoriously difficult to treat. He then handed me a *Buddhist Recitation Collection* and a CD, instructing me on how to recite Buddhist scriptures. He also taught me how to pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva before conducting recitations.

As I flipped through the book, I was captivated by the annotations explaining the purpose of each mantra and sutra. I realized I no longer needed to fear making mistakes in my recitations. Before, I had only known that after reciting scriptures I needed to dedicate myself, but I had been unsure of my methods.

The CD the doctor gave me was from 2013. When I returned home and played it on the television, I was overwhelmed. The melodious music and the sacred sounds surrounding Guan Yin Bodhisattva resonated deeply within me. It felt as if a lost child had finally found their mother, responding to Her call. Tears streamed down my face uncontrollably. I sobbed as if I had been reunited with my mother after years of separation. Seeing the sacred image of Guan Yin Bodhisattva—so dignified, compassionate, and magnificent—filled my heart with reverence. Master Lu's kind smile and His warm handshakes with fellow practitioners touched me deeply.

Master Lu's humility and wisdom transformed countless beings. His Dharma talks about alleviating suffering and guiding people toward happiness, helping them change their destinies. His ability to read totems was astonishing—by simply knowing a person's zodiac sign and birth year, He could reveal their fate and health condition.

With just a name, he could locate which realm the deceased soul resided. It was truly miraculous!

Every day, I watched the CDs for hours while going about my chores, completely engrossed. Whenever I had time, I read the Buddhist scriptures of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, studying them word by word, page by page, countless times. The teachings were incredible! I began reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra* and quickly memorized it within a few days. I first recited it for myself before gradually reciting it for my father.

Initially, I was unsure whether reciting scriptures would be effective, so I didn't inform my mother. Since Guan Yin Bodhisattva is invisible to the naked eye, I simply continued reciting with sincere devotion. Every day, I recited the four essential scriptures: the *Great Compassion Mantra*, the *Heart Sutra*, the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*, and the *Qi Fo Mie Zui Zhen Yan*.

After just one week, good news arrived—my mother called and said, "Your father's mouth is shaking much less now!"

This strengthened my faith even more. I knelt before the Buddhist altar at home and prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to bless my father and stop his tremors. After another week of recitations, I took the initiative to call my mother and ask about my father's condition. She responded, "Your father's mouth has completely stopped shaking. He is cured."

I was astonished! In just two weeks of recitations—without even starting Little Houses—my father's PD symptoms had disappeared without spending a single penny.

PD is known to be incurable in modern medicine, yet the recitations of Buddhist scriptures of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door proved to be extraordinarily effective! I was moved to tears.

However, in March 2018, my father's PD symptoms reappeared. This time, it was because he had attended a funeral and attracted a spirit. He was hospitalized again. Since my family still did not believe in Buddhism, he had no choice but to seek medical treatment. After more than ten days in the hospital with no improvement, he was discharged once more.

I then made a vow to recite 21 Little Houses for my father's karmic creditor. As I gradually burned and dedicated them, my father recovered once again!

In October 2018, my father was hospitalized for a third time. Since it was the Winter Solstice, he had visited the cemetery and once again attracted a spirit. This time, I vowed to recite 11 Little Houses for his karmic creditor. After completing and dedicating them, my father fully recovered for the third time.

Within two years, he was hospitalized three times for PD—an illness deemed incurable by modern medicine. Yet, through the recitation of four Buddhist scriptures and a total of 32 Little Houses, the crisis was completely resolved—without spending a single penny.

To all sentient beings who have an affinity with Buddha who are still hesitating outside the gates of Buddhism, do not waste any more time. Start reciting Buddhist scriptures now! The Dharma is an invaluable treasure that costs nothing but can change destinies.

I sincerely advise everyone to avoid attending funerals and visiting cemeteries, especially elderly individuals who are more vulnerable

to spirit attachments. If attending is unavoidable, one should recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* or chant the holy name of Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

Before encountering Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I suffered from chronic headaches, pain in both arms, gynecological issues, breast pain, and constant fatigue. After dedicating myself to this Buddhist practice, all these ailments disappeared completely.

Buddhist Practitioner: W89

Comments:

(1). Master Lu teaches us what the "Buddhist scriptures" we recite truly are [22].

Scriptures are the Dharmakaya relics of the Buddha. It is the scriptures possessed by the Dharmakaya that take effect on you, radiating brilliant golden light. Relics are something cultivated through spiritual practice, they are transparent and luminous. What Master sees is not from the human world but from the heavens.

That is why reciting Buddhist scriptures is one of the Dharma Gems of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

(2) Regarding why her father experience a recurrence of PD after attending a funeral, the following Q&A presents Master Lu's explanation of the underlying causes.

Q&A 4. Reasons for Avoiding Funerals (Excerpt)[23]

(This dialogue took place on Dec. 23, 2012 over phone.)

Caller: Hello, Master! It was mentioned before that one should generally avoid or minimize attending funerals. One reason is that it's easy for spirits to attach to you, but another reason—could it also shorten one's lifespan?

Master: If your lifespan is almost up or if you are facing a calamity, and you attend a funeral, the spirits there might notice you and attach to you. Why? Because these spirits, who are looking for substitutes, see that you are nearing the end of your life, and they might latch onto you, causing you to pass away sooner. Once you pass away, they can then reincarnate.

(3). Why did her father experience a recurrence of PD after he visited a cemetery during the Winter Solstice? We have previously discussed that even without visiting a cemetery, one may still be affected by spirits seeking karmic debts during this time [21, 24], let alone actually going there. This is especially true for an elderly person who is physically weak and has a history of PD.

Case 5. Buddhism Saved My Husband: From Bedridden PD to Complete Independence

My husband had been suffering from PD for 17 years. He was unable to take care of himself and required my assistance 24/7. Meanwhile, I was also struggling with severe lumbar disc herniation (LDH), with doctors recommending surgery. Adding to our distress, our son was diagnosed with coronary heart disease. Our entire family was trapped in a sea of suffering...

In August 2023, Buddhist practitioner Z, whom I had not contacted for a long time, suddenly reached out to me. Upon learning about my situation, she took me to the Buddhist Hall the very next day.

Through her explanation, I came to understand that my husband's

and my illnesses were due to heavy karmic obstacles. Before practicing Buddhism, my husband had followed his father in hunting birds during his childhood and also enjoyed fishing. I, too, had an abortion in the past. All of this was karmic retribution manifesting before us! When I realized that the suffering we were facing was a result of the negative karma we had created, I broke down in tears, overwhelmed with sorrow, and experienced excruciating headaches.

After listening to the patient guidance of fellow practitioners, I began reciting my daily scriptures, reciting Little Houses, studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, and making vows to release captive animals. In March 2024, I set up a Buddhist altar at home. After a period of practice, my husband's condition improved, my pain gradually eased, and everything started moving in a positive direction!

2024 marked my husband's predestined 369 calamity. During the Qingming Festival, his cousin passed away. After returning from the funeral home, my husband's condition suddenly worsened—he needed constant supervision 24 hours a day. Previously, medication could provide him temporary relief, but now he trembled nonstop day and night, and even medication no longer worked. I was utterly exhausted, barely sleeping for half a month.

Sometimes, when he wanted to use the restroom, I would struggle to help him there, only for him to refuse to piss once we arrived. Then, after much effort to bring him back, he would insist on going again—this cycle repeated endlessly. I already suffered back pain from LDH, and this constant strain left me completely drained. At that time, I was physically and mentally exhausted, losing the motivation to recite scriptures as diligently as before. I just wanted to sleep.

But Guan Yin Bodhisattva is incredibly compassionate! When I shared my situation with fellow practitioners, they encouraged me to have unwavering faith in Guan Yin Bodhisattva, assuring me that the Bodhisattva would certainly save me! They advised that since my husband's karmic obstacles were too severe, I needed to make great vows, as the power of vows is crucial. Therefore, in front of the Buddhist altar, my husband and I made the following vows:

1. Never kill sentient beings again, and eat vegetarian meals 10 days a month in addition to the 1st and 15th of the lunar month.
2. Release 1,200 fish per batch, continuously performing life liberation.
3. I recite 108 Little Houses for my husband's karmic creditors.
4. Recite *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*, *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots*, and *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou* 800 times each.
5. My husband would recite *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* once daily and read one chapter of *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, while I would help him recite *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* twice daily. A miracle happened the very next day! My husband was suddenly able to dress himself and go to the restroom independently! That night, he could get up and urinate on his own without my assistance. Occasionally, if he woke up unable to move, I would use a wheelchair to help him to the restroom. He even started taking out laundry from the washing machine to dry, cooking meals, and doing other household chores.

Guan Yin Bodhisattva is so compassionate! The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is incredibly efficacious! I was moved to tears! I am deeply grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate

Guan Yin Bodhisattva for mercifully blessing and protecting us, reviving my family, which was once on the verge of collapse due to illness, with newfound hope. After completing my first batch of Little Houses, I immediately vowed to recite another.

As my husband's condition improved, his medication intake gradually reduced. Previously, he had to take Madopar, Sifrol, Sinemet, and Amantadine daily, yet he still trembled uncontrollably all day long. Now, although he still needs medication daily, he only experiences tremors after the effects wear off, and the severity has significantly decreased. Consequently, his dosage has been reduced. For instance, he used to take five doses of medication daily, but now it has been reduced to four. Previously, he took three-quarters of a Madopar tablet each time, but now it has been reduced to half a tablet.

Now that my husband can take care of himself and handle household chores, I can finally get a full night's sleep!

He can even accompany me to Mountain B for exercise. Amazingly, he managed to climb to the top of the mountain on his own (Video 1).

On July 14, 2024, I made a vow to adopt a lifelong vegetarian diet! I was filled with Dharma joy—one good thing after another kept happening!

Now, my husband is also learning to recite scriptures. Every day, he recites *Great Compassion Mantra*, *Heart Sutra*, *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*, *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots*, and other scriptures 21 times. After finishing his daily recitation, he immediately begins reciting Little Houses. Initially, he could only complete one Little House per week, but recently, he has been able to finish one in 5-6 days.

Since he now helps with housework, I have more time for scripture recitation! My son's coronary heart disease was cured after I recited 108 Little Houses for his karmic creditors. Additionally, after reciting 216 Little Houses for my aborted children, my back pain disappeared, and I no longer needed surgery. It was truly miraculous!

I am deeply grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for saving my entire family! The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is absolutely real and effective, and the power of Little Houses is undeniable! I am grateful to Master Lu for imparting such an incredible Dharma Door to us. I am also grateful to my fellow practitioners who have supported and helped me along the way!

From now on, I will wholeheartedly follow Guan Yin Bodhisattva, cultivate my mind and practice diligently, never retreating in my faith. I will use my real-life experiences to inspire more destined sentient beings to be liberated from suffering and find happiness!

Shared by: C90

Comments:

(1). Regarding why the patient's symptoms worsened after attending his cousin's funeral, we have provided an answer in Q&A 4 in the comments of Case 3. This case further confirmed what Master Lu taught is true.

(2). Once again, the presentation demonstrated that the power of vows surpasses the force of karma, ensuring your salvation. This is precisely why 'making vows' is designated as one of the Dharma Gems in the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door [14].

(3). Repaying karmic debts requires the use of Little Houses. Taking 5-6 days to recite one sheet is kind of too slow. With heavy karma and such a slow repayment rate, it will take him a long time to recover.

(4). Why didn't he recover completely? Besides personal karma and repayment speed being a concern, he needs to vow to adopt a vegetarian lifestyle for the rest of his life.

(5). Master Lu enlightened us that LDH is a karmic/spiritual disease. We previously reported a case of LDH being cured through Buddhist practice [14]. This is the second case of healing after ascending children, further evidencing that killing karma is the root cause of LDH.

Discussion

PD is a formidable challenge for humanity due to its progressive nature and the lack of effective cures once diagnosed. The medical community's limited understanding of its underlying causes has resulted in symptom management being the primary treatment approach. For patients with severe symptoms, medications often become ineffective (Cases 2-5). In advanced stages, the intense physical and emotional suffering frequently confines patients to bed, significantly impacting their quality of life. As of 2021, approximately 11.77 million people globally were living with PD [25]. The burden this condition places on patients, their families, and caregivers is profound and cannot be understated.

Although PD is considered an intractable condition in modern medicine, from the perspective of Buddhism—particularly Master Lu's teachings—it is seen as a spiritual disease (Q&As 1-3). Addressing spiritual diseases remains an unexplored frontier in the medical field, but in Buddhism, especially within the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, a well-established and effective method for healing and saving lives has been developed. Even elderly individuals with limited education recognize that eliminating karmic obstacles and liberating spirits through Buddhist practices can restore physical health. Across various professions and backgrounds, many individuals have benefited from these practices.

To date, case studies have been published showcasing the successful application of Buddhist methods in treating intractable diseases [14, 15], including PD, among others.

The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door offers hope for alleviating the suffering of sentient beings and their loved ones by treating and, in some cases, curing such diseases. However, as previously discussed, curing a disease is not the highest form of wisdom; prevention is [26]. To prevent these conditions, it is essential to understand their root causes. In this regard, the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door provides profound insights. Master Lu, using His Dharma Eye, has discerned the spiritual causes of many rare and intractable diseases, offering a holistic approach to both prevention and healing.

PD arises from the eruption of karmic obstacles. When karma manifests, spirits attach themselves to the human body, leading to various illnesses, including PD. Although invisible to the naked eye, spirits possess formidable power. Beyond causing tremors, they can induce constipation [27], bradykinesia, rigidity, postural instability affecting walking [28], and a masked face [29]. When spirits afflict the neurons etc., these symptoms manifest. In Master Lu's on-the-spot totem readings, He revealed that some patients, due to prolonged attachment by spirits, gradually develop facial features resembling

those of the possessing spirit.

Thus, preventing PD requires addressing its root cause: avoiding the generation of karma. By cutting off the karmic source, the manifestation of PD can be averted.

Among the many sources of karma, killing karma is the most prevalent in the Dharma Decline Age [14]. Case 5 serves as a living example. As a child, the patient hunted birds with his father, enjoyed fishing, and his spouse underwent an abortion. In his later years, the eruption of these killing karmic debts led to an incurable case of PD. Why does Buddhism place the precept against killing as the first of the Five Precepts? The calamities caused by killing karma are far too widespread today. We must awaken to this truth, as the Buddha warned of the consequences of killing karma over 2,500 years ago [14, 30].

While the effects of killing karma on one's current life are easier to observe, its impact on future lives is less understood. Master Lu enlightened us that one's fate after death is determined not by wealth, status, power, or fame during life but by the balance of merits and karmic debts. A person burdened with heavy killing karma will face entanglement from karmic creditors after death, who seek retribution and cause immense suffering. Such individuals may also be sentenced to severe punishments in the underworld, endure ongoing retribution in their next life, or even descend into the lower realms, making liberation exceedingly difficult [31]. Our previous report of a child born with a genetic disease further validates Master Lu's teachings [32].

Life is precious, yet fleeting—spanning just a few decades. For the fleeting satisfaction of the palate, taking the lives of other sentient beings not only harms them but also brings immense suffering upon oneself. How tragic this is [31]!

The scientific community has yet to incorporate the effects of killing karma into research, though promising steps have been taken. For example, one psychologist observed that mothers who undergo abortions often have rebellious children [33].

Furthermore, some doctors have already begun recommending Dharma practice to patients. For example, in Case 4, the doctor directly advised the practitioner to use the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to help treat her father's PD. These developments mark a promising beginning and should be further explored. Scientists, especially medical professionals, embracing Buddhist teachings could also gain personal benefits, such as overcoming suicidal thoughts and behaviors, as discussed previously [21, 24].

From a logical standpoint, refraining from killing naturally leads to refraining from eating meat. True compassion requires not killing with one's hands and not consuming with one's mouth. Thus, adopting a vegetarian diet accumulates merits and virtues. For those suffering from severe or intractable illnesses, Master Lu advises them to make a vow as our first step: to abstain from killing and adopt a vegetarian diet. In other words, if one has already developed a severe illness yet continues to harm sentient beings without a compassionate heart, even Bodhisattvas cannot provide salvation. One must undergo a complete transformation and begin anew, starting with practicing compassion toward all sentient beings through vegetarianism.

Refraining from killing and not eating meat is merely the cessation of wrongdoing. For recovery from severe illnesses, one must also cultivate goodness. Following this logic, the next step is to practice

life liberation. According to the law of karma, if you have killed many sentient beings and accumulated negative karma, you must now save sentient beings to repay this debt. Regarding life liberation, many Buddhas and Bodhisattvas have provided profound teachings.

Guan Yin Bodhisattva enlightened us that "Life liberation is a supreme act of merit and virtue-making, encompassing financial giving, Dharma giving, and fearlessness giving in one complete practice while incurring minimal karmic burden. By offering life to others, you also create a path of survival for yourself. Moreover, it is a profound Dharma Gem to eliminate karma and dissolve negative karmic obstacles. May humanity strive to save sentient beings from the brink of death; this yields the highest merits and virtues. However, avoid pre-arranged purchases for liberation. Properly utilizing this Dharma Gem will extend one's lifespan, bring wealth and blessings, and fill life with Dharma joy [34].

Humans and spirits belong to different realms of existence, and spirits reside in the underworld. Master Lu teaches us to revere spirits while keeping a respectful distance. Collecting antiques is akin to associating with beings from the underworld. It will bring bad fortune to your home. Instead, invite Bodhisattvas into your home, and your life will improve in all aspects. On the subject of interactions with the spiritual realm, we have provided detailed explanations in prior articles, particularly those related to Autism Spectrum Disorder [26].

The successful cases presented in this article (Cases 1-4) and prior cases [15] prompt us to reconsider the conventional understanding of PD in medical science. Two key points emerge:

Contrary to the prevailing medical belief that PD worsens over time and is incurable, our cases suggest PD is reversible and curable after practicing Buddhism.

It is well known scientifically that the loss of mobility in PD results from dopamine deficiency [35]. To restore movement, neurons in the substantia nigra must regain their ability to produce dopamine in the brain [36]. The scientific community has explored various approaches to achieve this, such as deep brain stimulation (DBS) technology, which stimulates neurons to generate dopamine [37].

Patients recovering through Dharma practices should follow this same scientific principle but the effect is amazing. For example, in Case 1, the patient who previously required assistance to move suddenly walked unaided out of the Dharma Conference hall and even returned to the hotel independently after staying at the conference for a day. In Case 5, after making vows, the patient regained independent mobility overnight. It seems that practicing Buddhism can instantly activate the neurons' ability to produce dopamine—an astonishing phenomenon!

Others (Cases 2-4) also regained health after practicing Buddhism, further indicating that the restoration of dopamine production is independent of genetic factors, gut microbiota, or other known contributors. This suggests that the direct cause of PD lies in karma and spirits. Since Dharma practices can eliminate a significant amount of karma, any other factors, if involved, may only be secondary or manifestations of the underlying cause.

Given this understanding, describing PD solely as a "neurodegenerative disorder" fails to capture its essence. Instead, it should be redefined as a spiritual illness.

For instance, the current definition:

"PD is a prevalent neurodegenerative disorder characterized by

pathological changes, including the loss of dopaminergic neurons and abnormal aggregation of alpha-synuclein [38]."

Could be revised to:

"PD is a prevalent yet curable karmic and spiritual disease, marked by pathological changes such as neurodegeneration, including the loss of dopaminergic neurons and abnormal alpha-synuclein aggregation."

A long-standing mystery in the PD scientific community is why PD is associated with other diseases, particularly depression. Clinically significant depression is estimated to affect 35% of PD patients, with rates reaching 40.4% among outpatients and 54.3% among inpatients [39]. Our previous report [15] and Case 3 in this study also indicate a link between PD and depression. Scientifically, the explanation is highly complex, and the relationship between PD and depression appears to be intricately intertwined. This suggests that scientists have yet to uncover the true underlying mechanism of their connection.

From a Buddhist perspective, however, the answer is straight forward: severe depression and PD are both caused by spirits. A spirit can simultaneously induce both PD and depression in the same person, meaning their co-occurrence does not necessarily imply a cause-and-effect relationship. However, they can exacerbate each other.

Just as Master Lu enlightened us that "A true teaching takes one sentence, a false one fills ten thousand books." If we can grasp profound Buddhist wisdom from the simplest truths, that is the essence of "The Greatest Truths Are the Simplest (大道至简) [40]."

Similar to depression, other non-motor symptoms—such as loss of smell, constipation, and rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder—are also caused by karma and spirits. Even if these symptoms are attributed to PD, once the karma is removed and the spirits depart, patients can achieve full recovery and global health. This is exemplified in Case 2 of this study, as well as in our previous publication [15]. The same principle applies to other neurological diseases, such as ASD associated with ADHD [14, 26].

In an era that advocates holistic healing, the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door offers an ideal solution for those suffering from PD. Therefore, it is recommended to combine medical treatment with Dharma practice to address PD effectively and achieve a healthy, balanced life.

Recovery

Q&A 5. How Should Early-Stage PD Patients Recite Buddhist Scriptures [41]?

(Master Lu's Teachings: Answers to Letters of Inquiry (11) Question 15)

Inquirer: An elder fellow practitioner has just been diagnosed with PD. Should we treat this as a serious illness when reciting Buddhist scriptures?

Master: PD patient's soul is often at risk of being dragged down to the underworld. They frequently experience moments of unconsciousness.

Inquirer: The patient is in the early stages—he walks with small steps but has not reached the stage of trembling hands.

Master: This is like someone with a fever—once the fever starts, even if it is mild, it is already a sign of illness. When one knows they have the disease, it is already dangerous. Must you wait until all symptoms manifest? That is why I urge you to recite Buddhist scriptures now, while things are still manageable. Be vigilant and prepare for the challenges ahead. Recite as if dealing with a serious illness to prevent the disease from worsening. He should also recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*.

Q&A 6. How Should Late-Stage PD Patients Practicing Buddhism [42]?

(Master Lu's Teachings: Answers to Letters of Inquiry (478) Question 1)

Inquirer: A new practitioner is suffering from brain atrophy and PD. Medication has been ineffective. The individual has unclear speech, difficulty getting out of bed, and has been bedridden for five years, requiring two people to help him/her into a wheelchair daily. In such a case, how many Little Houses should be recited and how many fish should be released?

Master: This situation has already developed into a significant issue. It is recommended to recite over 800 Little Houses and release 20,000 fish.

Q&A 7. How to Recite Little Houses for PD [43]?

(This dialogue took place over the phone on March 2, 2012.)

Caller: Hello, Master! My father has PD. How many Little Houses should we recite for his karmic creditors?

Master: Start with 108 Little Houses in the first batch. Continue reciting until he recovers.

Caller: My mother and I will recite separately. Should we aim for a total of 108?

Master: Yes. After completing that, you should see noticeable improvement.

Caller: When burning the Little Houses, how should we pray Guan Yin Bodhisattva?

Master: Say, "May the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva bless my father [full name], grant him good health, and help him recover quickly from PD. Thank you, Guan Yin Bodhisattva, for resolving the karmic obstacles on my father's body."

Caller: Should we mention which Little House number we are burning today?

Master: That's not necessary.

Caller: How many Little Houses should we add for the second and third batches?

Master: Keep reciting without stopping.

Caller: Should we burn seven at a time as time permits?

Master: Yes.

Q&A 8. Significant Improvement in PD After Releasing Large Numbers of Fish [44]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on April 9, 2019.)

Caller: Hello, Master! I have a question about a disciple of yours

born in 1947, the Year of the Pig. He has been diligently practicing but has PD and trembles a lot. He can no longer attend Dharma events. He has recited over 2,000 Little Houses.

Master: There is an elderly lady spirit still attached to him. It hasn't left yet.

Caller: How many more Little Houses does he need to recite?

Master: He should continue reciting, about 280 more.

Caller: He has already released over 40,000 fish. How many more should he release?

Master: Releasing over 40,000 fish has already significantly improved his condition—he trembles much less than before.

Caller: Yes, that's true. He recites daily.

Master: Advise him to take calcium supplements; he has severe calcium deficiency.

Caller: Understood. How many more fish should he release?

Master: 3,800.

Caller: Alright. Thank you, Master!

Master Lu emphasized the importance of early and persistent recitation of Buddhist scriptures for PD patients, highlighting its ability to alleviate symptoms and prevent further deterioration. In early-stage cases, scriptures should be recited as if addressing a serious illness to halt progression. The *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* focused on repenting past wrongdoings, is particularly recommended.

For advanced PD with severe symptoms, Master Lu advised reciting at least 800 Little Houses and releasing 20,000 fish to address the patient's karmic obstacles. Recitation often begins with 108 Little Houses in the first batch, followed by ongoing recitation and additional batches based on progress. Prayers to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for health recovery and karmic resolution should accompany the burning of Little Houses.

In conclusion, making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation are essential practices for recovery from PD. Alongside Dharma practices, Master Lu advised adhering to doctor's recommendations, including taking appropriate medications and nutrients to address physical deficiencies associated with PD.

Master Lu underscored the importance of vigilance and consistent practice to address the spiritual and karmic dimensions of PD effectively.

Prevention

For PD, no specific discourse from Master Lu has been found. However, based on Master Lu's responses in Q&A programs and fellow practitioners' sharing in this article, we can summarize the following points.

Preventing PD requires addressing its root causes, which, according to Master Lu's teachings, stem from spiritual disturbances and karmic debts. By eliminating negative karma and avoiding activities that generate new karmic burdens, individuals can reduce their risk of developing PD. The key preventive measures are:

1. Refrain from Killing and Adopt a Compassionate Lifestyle

Killing karma is a primary cause of PD. Avoiding activities such as

hunting, fishing, and consuming meat helps prevent the accumulation of karmic debts.

Adopting a vegetarian or vegan diet cultivates compassion and reduces the burden of negative karma.

2. Avoid Interactions with Spirits and Negative Energy

Steer clear of places with heavy Yin energy, such as cemeteries and funeral homes, as they can attract spirits that may attach themselves and cause illness.

Avoid collecting antiques as they may harbor spiritual entities.

3. Practice the Five Golden Buddhist Practices [14]

One should engage in:

- (1). Making vows
- (2). Performing life liberation
- (3). Reciting Buddhist scriptures
- (4). Repenting of wrongdoings and refraining from repeating them
- (5). Reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*

These practices help eliminate karma and ascend spirits.

As one ages, accumulated karmic debts may manifest as illnesses like PD. Therefore, upon encountering the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, start practicing immediately. The earlier one begins practicing Buddhism, the more karmic debts will be eliminated, leading to a purer state in old age and a lower likelihood of developing PD.

Conclusion

PD remains a significant challenge in modern medicine due to its progressive nature and the absence of a definitive cure. While scientific advancements have provided insights into its pathology at the neuronal and biochemical levels, effective treatments remain elusive. However, from a Buddhist perspective—particularly through the teachings of Master Lu and the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door—PD is regarded as a karmic and spiritual illness, with neurodegeneration being merely a symptom caused by spirits.

The case studies in this paper highlight the effectiveness of Dharma practice in alleviating PD symptoms. By addressing the root causes—karmic debts and spirit disturbances—patients have experienced remarkable recoveries through making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation. These spiritual healing methods offer hope to those suffering from PD, serving as a complementary approach to conventional medicine and providing a holistic path to well-being.

The findings underscore the importance of recognizing the spiritual dimension of diseases like PD and integrating Buddhist wisdom into both prevention and treatment. As humanity continues its pursuit of health and longevity, embracing both scientific research and spiritual healing may unlock new possibilities for overcoming so-called "incurable" conditions.

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Conflict of Interest

No.

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Ethical Statement

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments and result analysis of the 5 patients. All the experimental procedures and practices by the 5 presenters were done by themselves independently.

Statement by translator and writer

The 5 cases and 8 Q&A dialogues from Master Lu's blog were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

Disclaimer of liability

The contents of the presentation, comments, and discussion, including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioners may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as medical advice or a diagnosis.

In the event of an emergency, it is crucial to promptly contact your doctor or emergency services by dialing 911. Relying on any information found in this paper is done solely at your own risk. The author bears no responsibility for the consequences. By using or misusing the contents, you accept liability for any personal injury, including death. It is imperative to exercise caution and seek professional medical guidance for health-related concerns.

References

1. Agostini F, et al. The Role of Virtual Reality in Postural Rehabilitation for Patients with Parkinson's Disease: A Scoping Review. *Brain Sci.* 2024 Dec 29;15(1):23. doi: 10.3390/brainsci15010023.
2. Russo M, et al. Biomechanics Parameters of Gait Analysis to Characterize Parkinson's Disease: A Scoping Review. *Sensors (Basel).* 2025 Jan 9;25(2):338. doi: 10.3390/s25020338.
3. Savall ASP, et al. *Eugenia uniflora* Effects on the Depressive-like Behavior of MPTP-Exposed Female Rats: Apoptosis and α -Synuclein Modulation. *Brain Sci.* 2025 Jan 3;15(1):41. doi: 10.3390/brainsci15010041.
4. Moshayed AJ, et al. Brain Stimulation Techniques in Research and Clinical Practice: A Comprehensive Review of Applications and Therapeutic Potential in Parkinson's Disease. *Brain Sci.* 2024 Dec 27;15(1):20. doi: 10.3390/brainsci15010020.
5. Mushta I, et al. Exploring the Potential Imaging Biomarkers for Parkinson's Disease Using Machine Learning Approach. *Bioengineering (Basel).* 2024 Dec 27;12(1):11. doi: 10.3390/bioengineering12010011.
6. Meindl T, et al. Assisted Parkinsonism Diagnosis Using Multimodal MRI—The Role of Clinical Insights. *Brain Behav.* 2025 Jan;15(1):e70274. doi:

- 10.1002/brb3.70274.
7. Yu B, et al. Deep learning-based differential gut flora for prediction of Parkinson's. *PLoS One*. 2025 Jan 7;20(1):e0310005. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0310005>.
 8. Zheng D, Chweon J. MicroRNAs in Parkinson's disease: From pathogenesis to diagnostics and therapeutic strategies. *Neuroscience*. 2025 Jan 22; 568:298-313. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2025.01.038.
 9. Gabrielli M, et al. The Role of the Gastrointestinal Microbiota in Parkinson's Disease. *Biomolecules*. 2024 Dec 28;15(1):26. doi: 10.3390/biom15010026.
 10. Pandey S, et al. Yoga-A complementary and traditional medicine for human health. *J Integr Med*. 2025 Jan 10;S2095-4964(25)00006-8. doi: 10.1016/j.joim.2025.01.002.
 11. Park MK, et al. Modulation of Second Messenger Signaling in the Brain Through PDE4 and PDE5 Inhibition: Therapeutic Implications for Neurological Disorders. *Cells*. 2025 Jan 9;14(2):86. doi: 10.3390/cells14020086.
 12. Zhang W, et al. Roles of NLRC4 inflammasome in neurological disorders: Mechanisms, implications, and therapeutic potential. *Pharmacol Ther*. 2025 Jan 22;108803. doi: 10.1016/j.pharmthera.2025.108803.
 13. Yu L, et al. Identification of novel phenolic inhibitors from traditional Chinese medicine against toxic α -synuclein aggregation via regulating phase separation. *Int J Biol Macromol*. 2025 Jan 14;297:139875. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.139875.
 14. Yang X. Treating Rare and Intractable Diseases via Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Health Sci J*. 2024 May 30;18(5):1137.
 15. Yang X. Healing Necrosis, Parkinson's, Arthritis, Depression, Migraines, and Pharyngitis via Dharma Practices. *Int J Nurs Health Care Res* 2024 Oct 21;7:1591.
 16. Madison CA, et al. 1,4-dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid prevents 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine-induced motor function deficits. *Behav Pharmacol*. 2025 Feb 1;36(1):40-46. doi: 10.1097/FBP.0000000000000806.
 17. Mohamed Yusoff AA, Mohd Khair SZN. Unraveling mitochondrial dysfunction: comprehensive perspectives on its impact on neurodegenerative diseases. *Rev Neurosci*. 2024 Aug 20;36(1):53-90. doi: 10.1515/revneuro-2024-0080.
 18. Lu JH. Questions and Answers: A Man's Parkinson's Disease Stemming from Emotional and Karmic Debts. Master Lu read the totem on October 12, 2018, at the New York Dharma Conference, USA.
 19. Lu JH. Questions and Answers: Collecting Antiques at Home Led to Parkinson's Disease. This dialogue took place over the phone on April 23, 2009. *Zongshu* 2009. 04.23; 48:54.
 20. Lu JH. Questions and Answers: Parkinson's Disease: Spirits Affect Both Health and Lifespan, and the Lifespan was Depleted. This dialogue took place over the phone on 2020 Jan 11; *Zongshu* 2020.01.11; 22:44.
 21. Yang X. Schizophrenia: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention. *Journal of Neurology and Neurosurgery*. 2025 Feb 15;1(1):1-22.
 22. Lu JH. Solemnly Adorning the Pure Land, Strict Teachers Cultivate Outstanding Disciples (2). *Buddhism in Plain Terms*. Book 3 Chapter 29, Pages 169-172. 2012.
 23. Lu JH. Questions and Answers: Reasons for Avoiding Funerals. 2012; wenda. 2012.12.23; A-09: 59.
 24. Yang X. Alzheimer's Diseases are Reversible from a Dharma Perspective. *Health Sci*. J2024 Jan 30; 18(6):1145.
 25. Luo Y, et al. Global, regional, national epidemiology and trends of Parkinson's disease from 1990 to 2021: findings from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *Front Aging Neurosci*. 2025 Jan 10;16:1498756. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2024.1498756>.
 26. Yang X. Autism Spectrum Disorder: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention. *J Medical and Clinical Case Reports* 2024 Dec 21;1(13).
 27. Hou X, et al. Disrupted Paraventricular Hypothalamic Nucleus Functional Connectivity in Parkinson's Disease With Constipation. *Neurogastroenterol Motil*. 2025 Jan 21:e15005. doi: 10.1111/nmo.15005
 28. Issa CTMI, Castro RD, Albuquerque KLGD. Cannabis oil in treating Parkinson's disease: improvement of motor and non-motor symptoms: a case report. *Braz J Biol*. 2025 Jan 17;84:e290305. doi: 10.1590/1519-6984.290305.
 29. Hou X, et al. A Markerless 2D Video, Facial Feature Recognition-Based, Artificial Intelligence Model to Assist With Screening for Parkinson Disease: Development and Usability Study. *J Med Internet Res*. 2021 Nov 19;23(11):e29554. doi: 10.2196/29554.
 30. Yang X. A Holistic Approach to COVID-19 Sequelae: Healing Through Dharma Practices. *Saudi J Med*. 2024 April 12;9(12): 517-522.
 31. Master Lu's Profound Dharma Talk Series: The Impact of Killing on Human Health (2) – 2014-07-23. Editor's Note from 2OR Secretariat.
 32. Yang X. Etiology and Treatment of Glutaric Aciduria Type I. *J Clin Med Img*. 2024 Sept 30;8(3): 1-13.
 33. Yang X. Oppositional Defiant Disorder: Underlying Mechanism and Solutions. *WebLog J Fam Med*. 2025 Jan 15; wjfm.2025.a1502. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15873702>
 34. Lu JH. Guan Yin Bodhisattva's Teachings on Life Liberation. Teachings from Buddhas and Bodhisattvas on Life Liberation. 2020 March 13;Wenda. 2020.03.13; 10:30.
 35. Li H, et al. An Intensified Regimen Containing Linezolid Could Improve Treatment Response in Mycobacterium abscessus Lung Disease. *Biomed Res Int*. 2019 Nov 19;2019:8631563. doi: 10.1155/2019/8631563
 36. Muñoz JM, et al. Morphological and functional decline of the SNc in a model of progressive parkinsonism. *NPJ Parkinsons Dis*. 2025 Jan 29;11(1):24. doi: 10.1038/s41531-025-00873-9.
 37. Benabid, A. L., et al. "Deep brain stimulation of the subthalamic nucleus for the treatment of Parkinson's disease." 2009 Jan; *The Lancet Neurology*, 8(1), 67-81. doi: 10.1016/S1474-4422(08)70291-6.
 38. Zheng D, Chen J. MicroRNAs in Parkinson's disease: From pathogenesis to diagnostics and therapeutic strategies. *Neuroscience*. 2025 Jan 22;568:298-313. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2025.01.038.
 39. Prange S, et al. Depression in Patients with Parkinson's Disease: Current Understanding of its Neurobiology and Implications for Treatment. *Drugs Aging*. 2022 Jun;39(6):417-439. doi: 10.1007/s40266-022-00942-1.
 40. Lu JH. The Greatest Truths Are the Simplest. Excerpt from Master Lu's Dharma Talk at the World Buddhist Friends Meeting. Jakarta, Indonesia. 2017 April 22.
 41. Lu JH. Questions and Answers: How Should Early-Stage Parkinson's Disease Patients Recite Buddhist Scriptures? Master Lu's Teachings: Answers to Letters of Inquiry (11) Question 15. 2011 Nov 7.
 42. Lu JH. Questions and Answers: Master Lu's Teachings: Answers to Letters of Inquiry (478) Question 1. 2015 July 6.
 43. Lu JH. Questions and Answers: How to Recite Little Houses for PD? 2021 March 2; *Shuohua*. 2012.03.02; 14:52.
 44. Lu JH. Questions and Answers: Significant Improvement in PD After Releasing Large Numbers of Fish. 2019 April 9; *Zongshu*; 2019.04.09; 17:52.